

Integrating Opinion Dynamics and Vortex Fields for Social Robot Navigation

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Abstract—Robotic navigation in shared environments requires a balance between safety and smooth motion. This study introduces a novel approach inspired by human social behaviour, integrating an opinion dynamics model for collective decision making with vortex fields and limit cycles for path planning. This combination allows robots to navigate more naturally and in accordance with social dynamics, outperforming traditional methods in terms of the quality of trajectories generated.

Index Terms—Human-aware motion planning, social human-robot interaction, opinion dynamics, potential fields, limit cycles.

I. INTRODUCTION

As autonomous robots become increasingly integrated into everyday life - from delivery systems in crowded urban areas to assistive devices in healthcare settings - it is crucial that they navigate alongside humans in a way that feels both natural and safe. Beyond simply performing tasks efficiently, robots must learn to share space with humans while respecting social norms and minimising disruption. Humans instinctively adjust their movements and communicate through subtle non-verbal cues to avoid collisions and maintain smooth paths. Emulating this delicate balance of navigation in robots is a significant challenge, requiring an understanding of human behaviour and the ability to generate adaptive, human-friendly motion paths.

Socially-aware robot navigation typically uses either reactive or proactive strategies. Reactive methods, such as the Social Force Model (SFM) [1], [2], enable quick responses to immediate changes, but often lack long-term planning and struggle with individual interactions. Proactive strategies, like opinion dynamics [3], allow robots to anticipate human movements and negotiate paths in advance, promoting smoother interaction but sometimes compromising real-time safety.

Despite the advancements in both reactive and proactive methods, existing approaches often treat these strategies in isolation, leading to gaps in effective navigation. In this work, we propose a unified approach that merges the strengths of both strategies to improve robot navigation in shared environments. By integrating social dynamics for decision making with vortex fields and limit cycles for trajectory planning, we aim to create a system that allows robots to navigate

complex environments while ensuring both safety and social appropriateness. Our primary contribution is therefore the development of a comprehensive navigation framework that effectively integrates negotiation-based decision making with smooth path generation. This integration enhances the robot's ability to adapt to real-time interactions with humans, leading to more intuitive and fluid movements in dynamic environments. Ultimately, this work aims to make robot navigation more effective and socially aware, paving the way for better integration of robots into everyday human environments.

II. METHODS AND RESULTS

Our approach to social robot navigation integrates two distinct but complementary strategies. First, we apply a model inspired by human-like opinion dynamics [3], which allows the robot to decide how to avoid obstacles - especially humans - by forming opinions based on social cues and proximity. As the robot approaches a human or obstacle, its attention level increases, resulting in more adaptive and smoother navigation. The opinion model determines whether the robot should move left or right: a positive opinion drives a counterclockwise trajectory, while a negative opinion leads to a clockwise trajectory (see Figure 1). This framework allows the robot to fluidly adapt to dynamic interactions with humans, avoiding collisions in a socially acceptable way. By dynamically adjusting its attention and opinion levels, the robot effectively avoids deadlocks. As the attention level rises near humans or obstacles, the neutral opinion state becomes unstable, pushing the system to decisively form a strong directional preference. This bifurcation mechanism ensures that the robot always makes a clear choice in ambiguous situations, preventing indecision or deadlock and allowing it to maintain continuous, smooth movement even in crowded or uncertain environments.

To further enhance safe and socially-acceptable navigation, we combine opinion dynamics with vortex fields and oval-shaped limit cycles [2]. Vortex fields generate repulsive forces around obstacles, guiding the robot safely away from potential collisions, while the oval-shaped limit cycles ensure that the robot avoids abrupt or unnatural movements. Unlike standard circular paths, the oval trajectories, defined by specific geomet-

Fig. 1. Passage preference, i.e., rotation direction γ , depending on the value of the opinion z : if $z < 0$, then $\gamma = 1$, i.e. the vortex field is clockwise; vice versa, if $z > 0$, then $\gamma = -1$, i.e. the vortex field is counterclockwise.

Fig. 2. Human-robot passing simulation: human and robot trajectories towards their goals (stars). The lines change from solid to dashed when the robot enters the limit cycle, i.e. when its attention level starts to increase.

ric equations, produce smoother, more human-like avoidance behaviour (see Figure 1). The shape and size of the oval adapt to the position and dimensions of obstacles, enabling efficient and fluid navigation even in complex and dynamic environments, where human presence is unpredictable.

Our method is designed to handle multiple users effectively by generating individual vortex fields for each nearby human. The robot prioritises its interactions with the closest human at any given time, adjusting its opinion and attention accordingly, while maintaining a general awareness of others in the environment. This dynamic prioritisation ensures that the robot can navigate through crowded spaces without sacrificing safety or social appropriateness, adjusting its path in real time to avoid collisions and maintain smooth motion.

Preliminary results. We validated this approach through simulations and real-time experiments. In simulations, the robot successfully adapts its path in response to the human’s behaviour, efficiently choosing the appropriate direction of rotation when the human’s movement is clear (see Figure 2), and choosing a safer, less risky route also in cases of uncertainty. This dynamic adaptability demonstrates that the robot could cope with different situations in human-robot interaction. For real-world validation, we conducted experiments with the assistive walker robot shown in Figure 3a in an

Fig. 3. The *FriWalk* assistive robot used in our experiments (a). Trajectories obtained from a real-time experiment (b).

indoor environment equipped with a localisation system. The robot interacts with humans in real-time, navigating smoothly whether the humans are cooperative or unaware. As shown in Figure 3b, the robot’s trajectory adapts to real-world conditions, closely matching the results of the simulations. The walker consistently maintains a safe distance from humans and gracefully avoids them, proving the effectiveness of the method also in experimental settings.

III. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This work proposes a novel socially-aware robot navigation strategy by combining nonlinear opinion dynamics with potential fields and limit cycles. This hybrid approach improves both navigation efficiency and social compatibility, addressing challenges that arise when these methods are used independently. The framework allows the robot to adapt proactively to human presence, ensuring effective collision avoidance and resolving deadlocks. Future efforts will focus on identifying human groups, enhancing adaptability, and handling more complex scenarios. Additionally, a key goal is improving how the robot communicates its intentions, allowing humans to understand and adjust their behaviour, fostering smoother interactions. Future experiments will also explore scenarios involving multiple agents to evaluate the system’s scalability and performance in crowded environments.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This project is co-funded by the European Union – Next Generation Eu - under the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP), Mission 4 Component 1 Investment 4.1 - Decree No. 118 (2/03/2023) of Italian Ministry of University and Research - Concession Decree No. 2333 (22/12/2023) of the Italian Ministry of University and Research, Project code D93C23000470005, within the Italian National Program PhD Programme in Autonomous Systems (DAuSy).

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